

TIMING FOR WORKS

Image: Starvation Black IPA. Preferred libation for artist-scholars. Photo: Gavin Keeney.

A COMPENDIUM

The following compendium of working documents and monographs concerns the mysteries of *where* to take works, plus the fact that works, in effect, often choose where they wish to go and *how* they wish to be edited.

RIGHTS + “NO RIGHTS”

Essentially “outtakes” from the PhD project, “Works for Works: ‘No Rights’” (2021-TBD), the premise of the following documents is that the 500-600-year history of intellectual property rights law is over and that artists and scholars (and artist-scholars) must now find a means to transfer moral rights to works, to protect works from misappropriation and exploitation. With moral rights having been the subtending chord for the 500-600-year history of intellectual property rights law, the facts “on the ground” show that they were slowly handed over to publishers and the capitalist commercium of cultural production, and/or neutralized and rendered “harmless” on behalf of publishers versus authors.

“OOI-MTA+++,” *Medium* (June 30, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/ooi-mta-4ae3e848d57b>

“The Abolition of Intellectual Property,” *Medium* (July 24, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/the-abolition-of-intellectual-property-652aa6142d26>

“Edition of One,” *Medium* (October 18, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/edition-of-one-5059f48380c4>

“Paradoxes of Discoverability,” *Medium* (November 27, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/paradoxes-of-discoverability-d04009a42ec9>

“Mad Mathesis,” *Medium* (December 3, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/mad-mathesis-90fc3b847a3a>

“Octopus Squids,” *Medium* (December 5, 2023)

<https://medium.com/@agencex/octopus-squids-6bbc62c57469>

ART-ACADEMIC CULTURE INDUSTRY

For a more detailed analysis of this shift in prospects for artists and scholars (and artist-scholars), see the following series of monographs, developed across: 1/ postdoctoral limbo (2014-2020); and 2/ a second doctoral project (2021-TBD). A third project in the series (perhaps a third PhD?) is currently envisioned toward developing a hyper-theoretical model for a new publications’ methodology entitled *The Edition of One* for works that *wish to have* absolutely no relation to capitalist or careerist agendas.

Knowledge, Spirit, Law: Book 1, Radical Scholarship (Brooklyn, NY: CTM Documents Initiative/Punctum Books, 2015)

<http://punctumbooks.com/titles/knowledge-spirit-law/>
<https://directory.doabooks.org/handle/20.500.12854/27518>

Knowledge, Spirit, Law: Book 2, The Anti-capitalist Sublime (Brooklyn, NY: CTM Documents Initiative/Punctum Books, 2017)

<https://punctumbooks.com/titles/knowledge-spirit-law-book-2-the-anti-capitalist-sublime/>
<https://directory.doabooks.org/handle/20.500.12854/29822>

Works for Works, Book 1: Useless Beauty (Earth, Milky Way: Punctum Books, 2022)

<https://punctumbooks.com/titles/works-for-works-book-1-useless-beauty/>
<https://directory.doabooks.org/handle/20.500.12854/90473>

FORTHCOMING – *Works for Works, Book 2: “No Rights”* (Earth, Milky Way: Punctum Books, 2024)

<https://punctumbooks.com/titles/works-for-works-book-2-no-rights/>

SEMAFORO

For a record concerning a reading of a set of divination cards in Venice, Italy, in April 2023, and “timings” concerning the last phase of the “Works for Works” project, see “Semaforo – Works-based Agency,” as below.

“Semaforo – Works-based Agency,” *Research Gate* (November 14, 2023)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375634796_Semaforo_-_Works-based_Agency

[...]